

Configurable and self-sufficient smart implants

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Abstract: A miniaturized motor driving an implantable distractor for mandibular osteogenesis has been developed. Due to the needs in respected to size, stroke and forces, a piezoelectrically driven inch-worm principle was selected to realize a miniaturized motor which allows a stroke of some millimeters. Wireless energy supply in combination with a rechargeable battery has been proven possible as energy supply concept. All components are encapsulated using a flexible bellow/tube out of parylene C coated latex or polyisoprene.

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I. Introduction

Distraction osteogenesis is a method to lengthen bones [1]. For this purpose, the bone is first fractured in a controlled manner, then both parts are joined with a mechanical distractor to maintain the correct position of the parts in relation to each other. Over a period of typical two weeks (in case of mandibular osteogenesis), the distractor moves the two bone parts up to 30 mm apart. New callus bone material is formed and fills the gap between the bone parts. The originally soft callus is transformed to solid bone within some months. During this time the implanted distractor as to ensure the mechanical stiffness and must absorb the forces acting on the bone (around 30 N).

Whereas, for femoral lengthening implants with integrated motors for distraction are already on the market, for example FitBone© [2], standard treatment for distraction osteogenesis of the mandibular until now is purely mechanical with a breakthrough of the implant through skin.

Here we present a configurable and self-sufficient smart implant for mandibular osteogenesis. The concept includes a miniaturized piezoelectrically driven inch-worm motor, a cableless energy supply with an additional implanted energy storage (battery) and a full encapsulation of all non-biocompatible components.

II. System concept

The main system components of a configurable and self-sufficient smart distractors for mandibular osteogenesis is shown in Fig. 1. Not shown is encapsulation of all components which contain non-biocompatible materials. The main components are the piezoelectrically driven miniaturized motors (II.1), the electronic control in combination with wireless energy transmission and battery-based energy storage (described in detail in [3]) and the system encapsulation (II.2)

II.1. Inch worm distractor

The miniaturized distractor is realized by a piezoelectric inch-worm motor consisting of a high precision guidance and three piezostacks embedded in specific patented spring

Figure 1 Schematic system approach of an implantable distractor for mandibular osteogenesis. The motorized distractor which pulls the two parts of the cut bone apart is inside the dark grey body. The energy is supplied by wireless transmission where a battery is used to reduce the energy transmission period to around 3h within 24h, from [3]. Modified from Theus / stock.adobe.com

Figure 2: Piezoelectrically driven inch-worm-motor, a) Realization of inch-worm within a monolithical guidance. The inch-worm-unit cell is placed into the guidance block b) By cyclic driving of the three piezostacks the unit cell moves step-like within the guidance. By design, the system is normally clamped, ensuring a secured position without applied voltage.

structures where two are for clamping and the central piezo provides the forward movement (Fig. 2). The unit cell of the inch-worm motor is the integrated clamping and driving unit shown schematically in Fig. 2 developed in a previous

project. The clamping parts are realized by two oval springs working in force amplification and attenuation mode [4]. The two piezostacks in the clamping units provide a stroke of $5,7 \mu\text{m}$ which are attenuated to a deformation of the oval springs by typically $3 \mu\text{m}$ by which the normally clamped springs are released from the guidance. The driving unit provides also a stroke of $5,7 \mu\text{m}$ which is the maximum step within one inch-worm cycle. Therefore, for e.g. 2 mm distraction per day only some hundred cycles are needed. The needed holding forces of around 30 N are created by friction between clamps and guidance (coefficient of static friction: 0,3 for Ti). The size of the guidance block is $6,5 \times 73,5 \times 18,6 \text{ mm}^3$.

II.2 Encapsulation

One requirement is long-term protection against liquids since moisture penetration would damage the electrically driven actor. The flexible encapsulation must also be expandable in the range of some cm. A bellow/tube-like shape is a promising concept. Latex and synthetic latex (polyisoprene) were tested as a suitable material. A method for producing these flexible and expandable samples out from liquid material on arbitrarily shaped moulds was established.

III. Results and discussion

Figure 3 Optimization of clamps to provide sufficient stroke for clamping. As example the influence of radius of oval structure on deformation is shown.

III.1 Distractor

The clamping unit was optimized by FEM simulation to

Figure 4 Characterization of miniaturized inch-worm motor: increment between the 6 steps within the inch-worm cycle. Inset: movement in forward direction over 5 cycles. The experimental stroke per cycle is $0,31 \mu\text{m}$.

provide clamping strokes sufficient for the given precision of fabrication of clamps and according guidance ($2,7 \mu\text{m}$, wire erosion). All critical design parameters and their influence on stroke were investigated. As example the influence of curvature of the oval spring structure on

deformation is shown in Fig.3 As a result, a structure was defined which allows a spring deformation for de-clamping of $3,2 \mu\text{m}$ for a piezo stroke of $5,7 \mu\text{m}$.

First measurements with a Michelson interferometer (Fig. 4) demonstrated the working principle of the miniaturized inch-worm-motor. However, the stroke (step 3) is only $0,278 \mu\text{m}$ and the total stroke per cycle only $0,31 \mu\text{m}$. Clamping (step 4) and de-clamping (step 2) actions have a strong influence, showing the need of further improvement of clamping stroke and spring stiffness for reliable operation and sufficient holding forces.

III.2 Encapsulation

Electrical insulation tests after long-term exposure to physiological buffered saline solution and sterilization with an autoclave showed sufficient insulation above 1,000 Volts for a wall thickness of 0.75 mm. Coating of latex and polyisoprene with parylene C led to improved mechanical compressibility. After autoclave-stress, parylene adhesion tests, electrical insulation tests and compression tests to check the elasticity of the bellow/tube-like systems were carried out. The measured stability of the electrical breakdown voltage showed the potential as an encapsulation material for electrically driven active bone distractors. [5]

IV. Conclusions

The first demonstrators of a miniaturized inch-worm motor principle and flexible bellows for encapsulation have shown the feasibility of the concept for an implantable distractor. Optimization of the inch-worm motor to achieve high reliability and a holding force of 30 N is required and is currently underway.

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